

Reactivities of some aldoses and aldosamines towards potassium bromate in hydrochloric acid medium

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The kinetics of oxidation of some aldoses and aminosugars by potassium bromate in hydrochloric acid medium have been studied. The reactions appear to proceed through the intermediate formation of bromate esters followed by the decomposition of the esters to give products. Hydrogen ion accelerates the rate of each reaction. The thermodynamic values associated with the equilibrium stage and the activation parameters associated with the rate-determining step have been computed.

The bromate ion oxidation of some alcohols¹ and α -hydroxy acids² have been investigated in acid media. The kinetics of the oxidation of some aromatic aldehydes³ by acid bromate have also been investigated and mechanism involving the formation of an unstable bromate ester which decomposes to the reaction products has been suggested. Surprisingly, the application of potassium bromate for oxidising organic compounds of biochemical significance is rather scanty. It may be mentioned that few preliminary kinetic data involving the oxidations of aldohexoses and aldopentoses at one temperature have been reported⁴ in perchloric acid medium although the mechanisms of these redox reactions are yet to be understood. Consequently, the oxidations of a number of polyhydroxy compounds by potassium bromate in hydrochloric acid medium have been studied under different experimental conditions in an attempt to have some ideas about their mechanisms and to compare the reactivities of cyclic aldoses with those of cyclic aldosamines.

Results and Discussion

The oxidation of aldoses and aminosugars by potassium bromate has been studied at various initial concentrations $(1.0-6.0) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of oxidant, keeping the substrate as well as hydrochloric acid concentrations and temperature constant at $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 1.0 mol dm^{-3} and 308 K, respectively. The pseudo-first order rate constant is independent of the initial concentration of bromate ion, indicating that the reaction is first order with respect to oxidant concentration (Table 1).

The effect of changing substrate concentrations has been studied at constant oxidant and acid concentrations. An increase of substrate concentration enhances the rate of oxidation. The plots of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against $1/[\text{substrate}]$ at different temperatures (303–318 K) give straight-lines (Fig. 1). These

Table 1. Values of pseudo-first order rate constant of different reactions under comparable conditions
[Substrate] = $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [Bromate] = $(1.0-6.0) \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and Temp. = 308 K

Substrate	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Glucose	6.05 ± 0.1
Mannose	7.26 ± 0.15
Galactose	8.45 ± 0.2
Xylose	9.42 ± 0.2
Arabinose	10.10 ± 0.3
Ribose	11.30 ± 0.35
Erythrose	12.80 ± 0.4
Glyceraldehyde	13.90 ± 0.4
Glycolaldehyde	15.60 ± 0.4
Glucosamine hydrochloride	4.07 ± 0.1
Mannosamine hydrochloride	4.97 ± 0.2
Galactosamine hydrochloride	5.93 ± 0.2

indicate that the reaction is initiated by the fast formation of an intermediate bromate ester followed by the slow decomposition of the ester to give products,

The equilibrium constants (K) associated with the substrate-oxidant equilibrium and the rate constants (k) associated with the slow step have been evaluated at different temperatures.

The reactions have been studied at different hydrogen ion concentrations varied by the addition of hydrochloric acid but at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), oxi-

dant and substrate concentrations. The plots of k_{obs} against $[\text{H}^+]$ for all the substrates are linear passing through the origin indicating that the order with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$ is unity (Fig. 2).

The enthalpy change (ΔH°) associated with equilibrium

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

step has been calculated from the plot of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 3) followed by the evaluation of ΔS° from $-\Delta G^\circ = RT \ln K$ and $\Delta G = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$. The activation enthalpy (ΔH^\ddagger) was

calculated from the $\log k/T$ vs $1/T$ plot (Fig. 4) followed by the estimation of entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) from the theory of absolute reaction rate as mentioned earlier⁵.

Thermodynamic values are recorded in Table 2. The enthalpy of activation has been found to be linearly related to entropy of activation. The isokinetic temperature has been calculated to be 321 K. The linear plot indicates that a similar mechanism may be operative in all the reactions. The isokinetic behaviour is also supported by the Exner plot of $\log k$ versus $\log k'$, where k and k' are the rate constants at

Table 2. Thermodynamic values associated with the equilibrium steps and activation parameters associated with rate determining steps*

Substrate	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Glucose	58 (40)	205 (-170)
Mannose	48 (37)	173 (-178)
Galactose	44 (35)	160 (-185)
Xylose	43 (32)	169 (-194)
Arabinose	42 (31)	155 (-197)
Ribose	39 (28)	147 (-207)
Erythrose	36 (27)	138 (-208)
Glyceraldehyde	35 (25)	136 (-214)
Glycolaldehyde	33 (22)	130 (-224)
Glucosamine hydrochloride	32 (41)	116 (-166)
Mannosamine hydrochloride	29 (40)	109 (-170)
Galactosamine hydrochloride	28 (38)	105 (-175)

*Figures in the parentheses represent the values of activation parameters (ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger)

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

303 (T_1) and 308 K (T_2), respectively. The isokinetic temperature⁶ (β) has been calculated from the relation, $\beta = T_1 T_2 (1-f)/(T_1 - T_2 f)$, where f is the slope of the Exner plot. The value of β has been found to be 338 K, and is higher than T , the mid-point of the experimentally used range of temperature. The value of $\beta-T$ which is positive, indicates that the reactions are governed by their enthalpies of activation in the temperature range studied⁷.

- [A] = β -D(-) Ribose, HO = b,c,f
- [B] = β -D(-) Arabinose, HO = a,c,f
- [C] = β -D(+) Xylose, HO = b,d,f
- [D] = β -D(+) Mannose, HO = a,d,f; CH₂OH = h
- [E] = β -D(+) Galactose, HO = b,d,e; CH₂OH = h
- [F] = β -D(+) Glucose, HO = b,d,f; CH₂OH = h
- [G] = β -D(-) Galactosamine, HO = d,e; NH₂ = b; CH₂OH = h
- [H] = β -D(-) Mannosamine, HO = d,f; NH₂ = a; CH₂OH = h
- [I] = β -D(-) Glucosamine, HO = d,f; NH₂ = b; CH₂OH = h

The rate increases with increases in $[H^+]$ and the order in $[H^+]$ is found to be one indicating that only one proton is involved in the reaction as per equilibrium reaction (3),

The present observation would be rationalised by the intermediate bromate ester formation. At constant acidity the rate equation is

$$\frac{d[\text{Oxidant}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{Oxidant}][\text{Substrate}]}{1 + K[\text{Substrate}]} \quad (4)$$

This is in keeping with the oxidation of some α -hydroxy acids² by the same oxidant in hydrochloric acid medium

Scheme 1

On the basis of the chair conformation of the sugars and their derivatives the following stereochemical structure is given :

which has also been shown to involve the intermediate bromate ester. In aqueous acid medium aldoses exist as an equilibrium mixture of the anomeric forms (α - and β -) of pyra-

nose and furanose along with the open-chain aldehydic form. The rate of formation of **IVB** should be slower than that of **IVA** due to steric hindrance of the axial hydrogens at C₃ and C₅ which is suggestive of the conversion of α -anomer to the β -anomer before the bromate ester formation thereby minimizing the involvement of **IVB** in the reactions (Scheme 1). The faster oxidation of the β -anomer is in conformity with the more favourable elimination of the proton from the axial position at (C₁) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

The oxidation of the sugar proceeds in all probability through the bromate ester which is formed by the easier esterification of the equatorial hydroxyl group (β -anomer) than that from sterically hindered axial hydroxyl group (α -anomer) at C₁. The α -anomer may be readily converted into the β -anomer prior to esterification. The bulky CH_2OH group in aldohexose should always be in the equatorial position (h) to minimise the steric interaction. The bromate esters (VI) then slowly decompose to the respective 1,5-lactones (VII) derived from the pyranose form of sugars. The lactones may open up to the corresponding open-chain hydroxy acids (aldonic acids) under the experimental conditions. Thus aldoses react initially with HBrO_3 to give aldonic acids and HBrO_2 . The latter by reacting rapidly¹ with excess substrates gives the reaction products and is itself reduced to HBr ,

The aldopentoses are more rapidly oxidised than the aldohexoses because of the ready formation of VI from aldopentoses. In the absence of bulky groups at C₅ in the aldopentoses the most crucial formation of the intermediate

bromate esters becomes easier than those from aldohexoses. It is also evident that the axial hydroxyl group in aldoses makes the oxidation faster, particularly when it is at C₂ thereby involving Delta-2-instability factor [in arabinose (B) and mannose (D)] which renders the oxidation (formation of sp^2 hybridised carbonyl at C₁ in place of sp^3) more facile.

Aldosamine hydrochlorides exist in aqueous solution in protonated form. Their existence in α - and β -anomeric forms

is different for different compounds. Thus for glucosamine, the more predominant form is the α -anomer (67%). With α -aminosugars (aldosamines) the axial OH at C₁ (α -anomer) may be stabilised by hydrogen bonding thus making bromate ester formation rather difficult. On the other hand, β -isomer reacts with bromic acid in fast equilibrium state and the rate of oxidation of the aldoses are slower than the parent aldoses. Hence, in general, the oxidations of the aldoses are slower than those of aldoses. Moreover, the axial OH groups at any carbon atom makes the oxidation faster than all equatorial (OH or NH_2 groups) isomers. In case of mannosamine, $-\text{NH}_2$ of C₂ being in axial position, β -anomer is in preponderant form. So the reactivity of mannosamine is greater than that of glucosamine. Thus bromate oxidations of aldoses and aldoses which have been studied in hydrochloric acid medium is kinetically dissimilar from metal ion oxidations⁸ of the same substrates. Consequently, present rate constant values cannot be compared obtained earlier with those oxidants. However, from the results it appears that bromate oxidation of aldoses occurs at measurable rates and hence bromate ion is in no way inferior to other oxidising agents in acid medium.

Experimental

All the organic compounds were of A.R. grade. Potas-

sium bromate (AnalaR) was used. The solutions of aldoses, aminosugars and potassium bromate were prepared in double-distilled water obtained by refluxing over potassium permanganate. All other inorganic compounds were of the highest purity available.

Rate measurements: The reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquots of the reaction mixture at known intervals of time and quenching the reaction by adding to it an excess of potassium iodide solution as mentioned earlier¹. During the oxidation, interference by the liberated bromine was prevented by adding a calculated quantity of mercuric acetate⁹ whereby the bromide ion formed from potassium bromate was removed as complex. The concentration of mercuric acetate was adjusted to 2.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ in each run. Mercuric acetate is inert towards oxidation of the aldoses and aminosugars. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were calculated from the slopes of log [bromate] vs time plots. Duplicate experiments were always reproducible with $\pm 5\%$. The errors were calculated as mentioned in the literature¹⁰.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of the oxidation of glucose by potassium bromate was determined as follows. A mixture of 10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ glucose (10 ml), 10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ potassium bromate (10 ml), 2.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl (25 ml) and 2×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ mercuric acetate (5 ml) was kept for 24 h at 35° for the reaction to complete. Excess of glucose was then estimated by standard Fehlings solution, and it was seen that 1 molar equivalent of potassium bromate oxidised approximately 3 molar equivalent of glucose under the experimental conditions,

To the products of oxidation, an aqueous ferric chloride solution coloured violet with phenol was added. A bright yellow colouration was developed which confirmed that aldoses are oxidised to the respective aldonic acids. The organic products were isolated and identified as mentioned earlier¹¹. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of the oxidation product with glucose in D₂O was recorded on a Bruker DPX-300

spectrometer (75 MHz) and the appearance of a peak at 178.8 ppm, which is in the region 163–184 ppm found¹² for different carboxylic acids, confirms the presence of gluconic acid. Similar experiments carried out with products obtained in the oxidation of the aminosugars by this oxidant, gave yellow colouration with the above reagent. It may be mentioned that aminosugars are also oxidised by mercuric oxide to give aldosaminic acids¹³ and that when iron(III) chloride solution coloured violet with phenol is added to aldosaminic acids, a yellow colouration is also obtained.

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